

**WHEAT TRIPSI (HAPLOTHRIPS TRITICI KURD)
PHLOETHRIPIDAE-PHLEOTHRIPID FAMILY THYSANOPTERA-
TRIPS ORDER BIOOGIAS AND COUNTERMEASURES**

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Introduction.

Wheat thrips causes great damage to wheat. As a result, wheat ears dry up. In some cases, the third part of them dries up, and the leaf does not write well. The leaf sheath does not develop well. The weight and quality of damaged grain is low. In some cases, if there is one larva of thrips in one grain, the crop will die by 11%, if there are three - up to 34-35%, and if there are five - up to 50%. Depending on the variety, the resistance of wheat is also different. Durum wheat is resistant to thrips.

The length of thrips is 1.5–2.2 mm. The body is thin, the last segment of the abdomen is elongated, and the back end is slightly narrowed. The middle part of the front thorax is slightly narrowed like that of other thrips, and the edges of the wings have long spines.

The mustache has 8 joints, its body is black, 3 joints are flowing, and the tip is slightly brown. The thrips larva is thin, up to 2 mm long, the mustache has 7 joints, the spine on the last joint of the abdomen is shorter, the larva is light red in color.

Wheat thrips hibernates under soil clods, in cracks in the earth in the young larval period. In early spring, when the temperature reaches 8°C, the larvae begin to move and feed.

Adult thrips appear in April. By the middle of May, they are observed to be very numerous, and at this time egg-laying is at its peak. The female thrips lays one egg, sometimes several, on the spikelet, sometimes on the shell. Adult thrips live by sucking the tip of the stem and the leaf sheath of the wheat plant. 6-7 days after laying the eggs, the larva emerges. Larvae enter the shell of the spike and begin to suck the shell and flower juice. Later, they begin to suck the juice of the grain.

In addition to wheat, these thrips damage barley, oats, corn and other cereal grasses. They breed once a year. In order to fight against them, it is necessary to thoroughly plow the land, introduce crop rotation and use chemical means. BI-58 40% em.k. 0.5–1 l/ha; karate 5% em.k. 0.15–0.2 l/ha; fallow 40% em.k. 1.5 l/ha; syracuse 25% em.k. 0.2 l/ha is used.

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